

Integrating Globus and Tapis*

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Steve Black

*Texas Advanced Computing Center
University of Texas at Austin
Austin, Texas*

Kevin Price

*Texas Advanced Computing Center
University of Texas at Austin
Austin, Texas*

Richard Cardone

*Texas Advanced Computing Center
University of Texas at Austin
Austin, Texas*

Joe Stubbs

*Texas Advanced Computing Center
University of Texas at Austin
Austin, Texas*

Kyle Chard

*University of Chicago
Chicago, Illinois*

Rachana Ananthakrishnan

*University of Chicago
Chicago, Illinois*

Abstract—Performing scientific research on high performance computing infrastructure often requires processing large data sets. Supporting transfer of large amounts of data in a gateway can be a complex, error prone, and time consuming process. Globus is a hosted software service that, among other features, supports fast, secure, and reliable transfer of data. This paper describes the integration of Globus support into Tapis, a web-based, hosted platform used by researchers from multiple institutions to perform scientific research and build gateways. We also discuss how the integration facilitates the use of two Globus endpoints as part of running a job in Tapis.

Index Terms—data transfer, HPC, cyberinfrastructure

I. INTRODUCTION

We describe the integration of Globus [1] into the Tapis framework [2], [3]. This integration enables gateway developers and Tapis users to transparently stage data between diverse external resources, such as cloud storage, HPC clusters, and personal computers. Integration provides streamlined access to the approximately 40,000 active Globus endpoints around the world without having to manage credentials (such as SSH keys) for each resource.

One of the challenges in integrating Globus and Tapis is to address the separate authentication schemes used by each component. In addition, the Tapis Files service has to be enhanced to support asynchronous transfer outside its framework. We cover the following:

- Creation of a Tapis Globus proxy service to facilitate use of Globus in Tapis services.
- Enhancement of the Tapis Systems service [4] to work with Globus authentication [5] in order to obtain, manage, and refresh Globus tokens.
- Enhancement of the Tapis Files service [6] to support synchronous file operations (such as listing, delete) and asynchronous file transfers through Globus.
- Execution of application code through the Tapis Jobs service [7] using two Globus endpoints, with the tar-

get endpoint configured as a Tapis data transfer node (DTN) [8].

II. MOTIVATION

This integration will benefit gateway developers and the many thousands of users and workflows that use Tapis and Globus. Tapis Workflows [9], a service which provides support for application pipelines, is currently under development. It is being used in several projects [10], including Tuitus [11] and HETDEX [12].

Another project we are targeting with this integration is the NEID astronomical spectrograph developed jointly by NASA and NSF [13]. The Jet Propulsion Laboratory currently transfers data using Globus and then runs Tapis jobs as part of an extract-transform-load (ETL) [14] pipeline. We expect Tapis/Globus integration to simplify the pipeline.

III. BACKGROUND

Globus and Tapis are web-based, cloud-hosted platforms that serve the research and engineering community. Collectively, Globus and Tapis serve 200K+ users and provide methods to easily manage data and computation across a heterogeneous and distributed research landscape. However, while the platforms have had significant individual impact, they operate independently and place the burden on developers and users to do the integration. This can lead to cumbersome, brittle, and in some cases, insecure workflows.

Tapis supports various technologies and protocols for managing data on remote resources, including SFTP, iRODS [15] and S3. Tapis provides a data management API that specifies methods for synchronous and asynchronous transfer. These APIs incorporate the Tapis authentication and permissions framework. Tapis also provides an API for remote execution of tasks that also uses this authentication framework.

Globus provides managed and high performance data access, sharing, and third party data transfer between Globus enabled storage systems. Globus endpoints or *collections* serve as interfaces to heterogeneous storage systems, providing a

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uniform interface for data access (via HTTP/S) and high performance transfer between endpoints (via GridFTP). Globus offers a comprehensive OAuth-based identity and access management platform for brokering access between users and services, user workflows for delegating consent, and an identity federation model with usage policies. Globus's OAuth SSH model builds upon Globus Auth to provide OAuth-based SSH capabilities that remove the need to manage SSH keys.

IV. INTEGRATING GLOBUS AND TAPIS

In this section, we discuss enhancements made to existing Tapis services to support the integration of Globus into Tapis. At a high level, this integration involves the creation of a Tapis Globus proxy service and updates to the Tapis Systems and Files services.

A. Creating a Tapis Client Application for Globus

As discussed in the Globus Auth Developer Guide [16], to integrate a client application (in this case Tapis) into Globus, the application developer must create a project in Globus and register the application. This yields a Globus client ID that gets configured as part of the Tapis environment. Each Tapis installation can be configured with its own Globus client ID. For more information on installing Tapis at multiple sites please see the online documentation [17].

To use Globus, an end-user will create a system in Tapis and follow an authentication flow to register credentials for the system. The Tapis client application uses the Globus OAuth2 *Native App* flow to obtain the initial access and refresh tokens for the end-user. Globus's support for the PKCE protocol is used to perform a three-legged OAuth2 authorization code grant [18].

B. The Tapis Globus Proxy Service

Tapis services that need to use the Globus API are written in Java and other languages, but the supported Globus SDK is written in Python. We considered several approaches when deciding how to integrate the platforms, including calling the Python SDK directly from native code, making REST calls from native code, and developing a separate standalone proxy service.

We chose to implement a standalone *Globus-Proxy service* in Tapis [19]. It acts as a communication intermediary between Tapis services and Globus. The proxy service is written in Python.

The proxy approach provides a lightweight and stateless approach. It also simplifies updates to other services since there is already shared code to support service to service REST calls within Tapis. The resulting Globus-Proxy service implements a one-to-one relationship between the Tapis API endpoints and calls made to the Globus API.

C. Enhancing the Tapis Systems Service

The Tapis Systems service [4] supports multiple types of "systems," some of which are only for storing data. The initial release of Tapis supported types LINUX, S3 and iRODS. For

integration, we defined a new type of system: GLOBUS. The model and implementation of the service has been enhanced as follows:

- For a system of type GLOBUS the **host** attribute is interpreted as the Globus endpoint or collection ID.
- The Systems Credential model [20] supports a new authentication type called TOKEN with the additional attributes *accessToken* and *refreshToken*.
- A new Systems API endpoint returns a URL to be used by the end-user to obtain an OAuth 2 authorization code and session ID. Endpoint: *credential/globus/authUrl*
- A new Systems API endpoint accepts the authorization code and session ID as path parameters and uses them to obtain a Globus access+refresh token pair. The tokens are never exposed to the end-user. The Systems service records them as part of the end-user's credentials record. Endpoint: *credential/{systemId}/user/{userName}/globus/tokens/{authCode}/{sessionId}*

The Systems service implements these API endpoints by making calls to the Globus-Proxy service.

D. Enhancing the Tapis Files Service

The Tapis Files service [6] is the central point of interaction for all file and directory operations in the Tapis ecosystem. The service supports synchronous operations such as listing and *mkdir* as well as asynchronous transfer between systems. Not all operations are supported for all system types. The service has been enhanced to support the following operations for GLOBUS type systems:

- listing
- mkdir
- move
- delete
- transfer between GLOBUS systems

All operations except for transfers are handled synchronously by Tapis. For these operations, the service has been enhanced to make and manage calls to the Globus-Proxy service.

File transfers [21] are handled asynchronously using a separate worker thread for each transfer. To support Globus, the following enhancements were made:

- Transfers involving Globus require that both the source and destination systems be of type GLOBUS.
- Addition of the attribute *externalTransferId* to the transfer record model. Used by the worker thread for monitoring and cancel operation.
- Update the worker thread to monitor the external transfer and update status.

V. END-USER AUTHENTICATION FLOW

When a Tapis end-user wishes to register credentials for a Tapis Globus system they will use the following flow:

- 1) User calls the Tapis *authUrl* endpoint in order to determine the URL that can be used to obtain an authorization code.
- 2) User visits the provided URL and is presented with a Globus logon page that will allow them to authenticate using one of thousands of supported identity providers, including through their existing organization using CI-Logon [22], [23].
- 3) After authentication, user is re-directed back to a Globus page showing the access being requested by Tapis.
- 4) User fills in a label for future reference and clicks *Allow* to authorize Tapis to access Globus on their behalf.
- 5) User is shown an authorization code valid for a short time (currently 10 minutes) that must be passed to Tapis.
- 6) User calls the Tapis credential endpoint to exchange the authorization code and session ID for tokens which are stored by the Systems service in a credentials record.

At this point the end-user has defined a Tapis system that can be used as a source or destination for Globus operations.

VI. TRANSFERRING DATA BETWEEN GLOBUS ENDPOINTS USING THE TAPIS FILES SERVICE

Once a user has defined two Tapis systems of type GLOBUS, it is simply a matter of following the authentication flow described above for each system. From that point on, the user may submit a transfer request and it will be handled in the same manner as any other Tapis transfer. There are no end-user visible changes to the Files API.

VII. RUNNING A TAPIS JOB INVOLVING GLOBUS ENDPOINTS

When running a Tapis job, files are typically transferred from one or more source storage systems directly to the target execution system. For a Globus source storage system, Tapis will initiate a transfer via Globus to a Data Transfer Node (DTN), a specialized high-throughput system running a Globus endpoint. The jobs service will coordinate the transfer such that, from the running application's point of view, data from the source Globus system is available on the execution system.

The 3 systems involved in the transfer are the source Globus endpoint, the target Globus endpoint (DTN), and the execution system. Figure 1 shows the 3 systems involved along with 2 additional storage systems used for staging input data.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The integration of Globus and Tapis allows users to configure and use Globus endpoints and collections just as they would any other storage system. Combined with Tapis workflow support it also facilitates automation of projects that involve managing multiple jobs, such as extract-transform-load (ETL) pipelines.

In the future, we plan to improve handling and reporting of various error conditions, such as endpoint not found, endpoint needs re-activation, etc. We will also be working on support for pausing and resuming a transfer to allow for endpoint activation during the execution of a job.

Fig. 1. Data Transfer Node Configuration

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